

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: University of Leeds

Detecting and Locating Seismicity
using Machine Learning

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1 Executive summary

1.1 Challenge overview

Detecting the occurrence and location of earthquakes is vital in a variety of settings. An increase in seismicity (waves generated by earthquakes or rupturing) in volcanoes indicates changes in behaviour which then inform decisions on eruption likelihood and whether evacuation is necessary. Recently, seismic activity has been linked to potential geothermal activity [5] and thus is a promising method for evaluating a location for a geothermal power plant. Ruptures in glaciers generate seismic activity and analysing and locating these signals give a non-invasive method to understanding the dynamics and structure of glaciers. The tragic incidents of the 2023 earthquake in Turkey also motivate the rapid and accurate detection and location of seismicity both before and after the main earthquake; the aftershock earthquakes map out the fault structure beneath the surface and highlight regions where events are likely to take place in the near future.

Automating the detection of seismic arrivals is useful in a variety of fields but it has yet to be perfected and many approaches, including those using deep learning, have been trialled. Techniques that will rapidly detect and locate seismicity automatically are still computationally expensive, require human intervention, or rely on uncertain information about the geological structure [e.g. 3]. Other studies have used neural networks to extract the arrival time of the seismic waves caused by the earthquakes and then give these times to techniques typically to locate where the rupture occurred [e.g. 8]. These approaches only use one seismogram at a time and information about the seismometer's location is rarely used. Furthermore, issues remain with assumptions of accurately predicting the time taken for waves to pass through the subsurface from the earthquake to the seismometer.

This challenge involves both identifying seismic arrivals in time series data of ground motion at seismometers and then locating said arrivals in terms of their latitude, longitude, and depth. Meeting this challenge would mark a huge improvement in our ability to monitor earthquakes and manage the risks they pose. Aspects of this work, such as identifying useful features or the neural network architecture, could be translated to and improve other

fields.

1.2 Data overview

The data given in this challenge is continuous ground motion recordings lasting three weeks from the 4th to the 25th of July 2019. The target dataset is made up of the tens of thousands of aftershock events caused by two large earthquakes that ruptured on the 4th and 6th of July in southern California, leading to mass disruption and damage in the area. This earthquake sequence has been heavily studied using various approaches and a high-resolution catalogue of earthquake time and location (latitude, longitude, depth) has been made [9], incorporating extra information such as models of the local geology. Due to the density of data in space and time and the availability of high-quality ground truth data, this is the region of interest we worked with.

The ground motion data for each day covers the same time period time from 00:00 on the 4th of July 2019 to 00:00 on the 25th of July 2019 and has a sampling rate of 100 Hz (100 samples per second). The ground motions are recorded in three different planes, a North-South plane, an East-West plane, and a vertical plane. Some basic preprocessing has been done such as removing seismometer biases, so all seismograms have the same amplitude and are complete. The raw data is publicly and freely available from EarthScope Consortium Web Services <https://service.iris.edu/>.

1.3 Main objectives

In the context of detecting and locating seismic activity automatically. The specific goals of the challenge are as follows:

- Given a time series of ground motion, detect the time periods where earthquakes may have occurred.
- If seismic activity occurs, locate where the earthquake may have occurred.

1.4 Approach

There are two tasks associated with this challenge and we explore a variety of approaches to solve each.

For the detection problem, we first extract features such as the minimum amplitude, maximum amplitude, standard deviation, kurtosis, and median absolute deviation. From these features for each 10-second time window, we then train various classical machine learning models, such as random forests, to determine whether an earthquake has occurred. We also explore an unsupervised approach by using information theory and graphical network analysis to infer the temporal variation of seismicity.

For the location problem, we extract the times of arrivals at each station for windows where the signal has been identified and use these, along with station location, to train models to locate events. The approaches include random forests and dense neural networks. We also use CNNs with the unprocessed time series of ground motions at each station with the station locations to locate the earthquakes. Physics-informed neural networks were explored but not successfully implemented.

1.5 Main conclusions

- Analysing the data in a graphical sense where the nodes represent a seismometer and the edges may feed information between them but physically it is unclear what this would be, we found each of the 17 stations contributed differently to the recording of seismic activity.
- Temporal analysis of seismicity in the data shows peaks in seismic activity early and late in the day.
- Random forests performed best in identifying earthquakes from the statistical features extracted from the waveforms. Other approaches, such as support vector machines, did not perform well possibly due to noise in the data.
- When locating the earthquakes, the longitude was better predicted than the latitude for both random forests and convolutional networks.

- Random forest regression performed well using only estimated arrival times of the wave at each of the seismometers and the seismometer locations.
- The convolutional neural network showed great potential to locate earthquakes directly from waveform data and achieved a mean latitude error of 0.0627 (7.00 km) and a longitude error of 0.0812 (5.46 km). This is a promising result as it matches current accuracies with room for refinement and more complex network architectures.

1.6 Limitations

Time constraints meant not all avenues were explored and some changes in feature extraction could be made to improve the quality of the models trained. The time extraction process from the seismograms was very basic and probably led to very large errors. The lack of filtering on the seismograms most likely meant noise heavily affected our results. Most of the neural network implementations required precise input shapes, so data of a different sampling rate or a different number of stations could not be used. The trained models will not generalise well to other locations or scenarios where the geology is most likely very different.

1.7 Recommendations and future work

- More features and window sizes should be trialled for detecting earthquakes.
- Random forest detection of earthquakes requires more investigation to see if low-magnitude events are being detected mistakenly.
- Analysis on the generalisability of these techniques to locations such as volcanoes and identifying signals from the deeper Earth is needed.
- Expanding analysis on earthquake location to be able to take inputs of different sizes (i.e. if more or fewer seismometers are available) would be very useful also.

- Training on all data originally given would provide more insight into the performance of these models.
- Convolutional neural networks directly from seismograms to event location seem to be promising, and should be developed to include depth in their location predictions.

2 Data overview

The data for this project consists of ground motion data from station seismometers around the Ridgecrest area of Southern California, US. The data is recorded for three weeks continuously at a sampling rate of 100 Hz with the goal of detecting seismicity from aftershocks of the main Ridgecrest earthquake. Each file contains data from one day measured in one of three channels, with each channel recording the motion in different directions (north-south, east-west, and up-down). This is time series data that describes ground displacement as a function of time. An example of these waves can be seen in the 10-second window plots in Figure 1. The plots on the left correspond to normal ground activity, while the ones on the right include an earthquake.

Ground truth in terms of earthquake occurrence and location comes from a high-resolution catalogue created by multidisciplinary analysis of the region to identify and locate earthquakes. This dataset contains the date and time of the earthquake, its location (longitude, latitude and depth), as well as its magnitude. A sample of it can be seen in Figure 2. The locations of all events in the catalogue and seismometers are shown in Figure 4.

Finally, we have used a location table (longitude, latitude and elevation) for all the operating stations in the area and the file names associated with these locations (Figure 3).

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Figure 1: 10-second window plots of the ground motion data. The plots on the left do not show an earthquake, while the plots on the right do.

	year	month	day	hour	minute	second	lat_reloc	lon_reloc	depth_reloc	mag
0	2019	7	4	11	51	8.099	36.11160	-117.66895	3.757	0.73
1	2019	7	4	16	7	20.315	35.70531	-117.49551	11.320	0.50
2	2019	7	4	16	13	43.404	35.70529	-117.49534	11.340	1.50
3	2019	7	4	17	2	55.456	35.70806	-117.49754	11.366	3.98
4	2019	7	4	17	9	20.158	35.70658	-117.49545	11.319	2.49

Figure 2: Sample of earthquake log dataset

	filename	lat	lon	elevation
0	CI.CCA..HHE.npy	35.15252	-118.01649	710.0
1	CI.CCC..HHE.npy	35.52495	-117.36453	670.0
2	CI.CLC..HHE.npy	35.81574	-117.59751	775.0
3	CI.DAW..HHE.npy	36.27148	-117.59214	1477.4
4	CI.DTP..HHE.npy	35.26742	-117.84581	908.0

Figure 3: Sample of stations dataset

3 Data exploration

3.1 Spatiotemporal patterns of seismic activity

Each of the seismometers records ground motion data at specific locations across California. When an earthquake occurs in the region, many of these stations may record similar variability in the ground motion signals as the wave propagates through the ground beneath the seismometer. This shared variability is of particular interest as it may reveal exactly where and when the earthquakes were experienced across the various locations. To pursue this insight further, we undertook the following analysis of July 4th ground motion data from 17 measurement stations.

Spatiotemporal network-information extraction

Data recorded on the 4th of July from 17 measurement stations were used for this analysis. We found the triple cross-product of the three

Figure 4: Distribution of seismometers (green triangles) and earthquake locations (blue circles) for the full Ridgecrest earthquake sequence between July 4th and 25th 2019.

channels recorded at each station (i.e. (North-South x East-West) x Up-Down)), resulting in a single vector for each station representing ground motion in 3D space. We then filtered these vectors within the range of 0.01-20Hz, as most seismic activity is thought to manifest within this range. The filtering we used was a combination of a low-pass and high-pass 4th-order Butterworth zero-phase filter [1]. We then cut the filtered data into separate time windows of 1000 samples (10 seconds).

To determine the network-level interdependencies, we computed the mutual information [4] between all unique pairs of stations (e.g. stations X

and Y) within corresponding time windows. Mutual information (MI) quantifies the information (or improvement in predictability) about the ground motion at station Y when observing the ground motion at station X and vice versa and can be interpreted as a generalised Spearman's rank correlation that captures both linear and non-linear relationships between random variables. We repeated this procedure for all time windows, resulting in a matrix of size [n_rows: No. of unique station pairs, n_columns: No. of time windows].

Identification of significant shared seismic variability

To identify the statistically significant dependencies, we reshaped each row of this matrix into a [No. of stations x No. of stations] symmetric matrix and applied a modified percolation analysis. This approach thresholds network connectivity (i.e. sets insignificant connections to zero) that would be present in an equivalently sized random network, bringing the empirical network closer to the percolation threshold, a critical value that complex dynamical systems are thought to fluctuate around.

Dimensionality reduction

To empirically determine the number of components to extract from this sparsified set of networks, we concatenated them together as layers in a multiplex network. We then implemented a community detection protocol that seeks to find representative clusters of network connectivity using a modularity maximising cost function. It was found that the nodes representing each of the 17 stations were highly overlapping in their network structure, resulting in a single identifiable cluster without any definable features. Therefore, we implemented a link-based community detection approach that first unravels the hierarchical structure of each layer in the multiplex network and then determines the optimal community structure.

From this detection protocol, we identified no modularity among the measurement stations, meaning that each of the 17 stations contributed differently to the recording of seismic activity. This finding, in light of the previous single module identified, reveals a shallow hierarchy of network connectivity, where the stations appear globally to be functionally similar,

however locally, they process unique geophysical information. With this finding, we extracted 17 components from the sparsified networks using projective non-negative matrix factorisation. These components do not correspond to each individual measurement station but instead capture representative patterns of interdependencies between measurement stations.

Selection of most relevant patterns

Having extracted representative spatio-temporal patterns of seismic activity, we then sought to determine the most predictive patterns of the occurrence of an earthquake event. To this end, we created a binary variable equal in length to the number of time-windows used in the analysis. A value of 1 in this variable indicated the presence of earthquake magnitude seismic activity while 0 indicated otherwise. This variable served as the target in the following feature selection protocol. Using the Catboost Classifier algorithm, we determined the classification performance of the 17 components simultaneously. The input predictors for this classification problem were the temporal components of the dimensionality reduction output (rows), illustrated in Figure 5.

To correct for the imbalance in the data (very few time windows corresponded with an earthquake event throughout the recorded day), we implemented the SMOTE python package which synthetically oversamples minority classes in a dataset. From this, we determined the Shapley value for each pattern. The findings of which are illustrated in Figure 6. As one can see, high values of shared motion variability between measurement stations increase the probability of an earthquake event being observed, most notably for components 12, 9, and 0.

To complement this finding, we illustrate the top three components and their geographic mappings (Figure 7). The three spatial networks of measurement stations describe three distinct patterns of dependency centred around the motion variability experienced at one station in each of the subplots. Furthermore, their corresponding co-variations across time are depicted in Figure 8, which describes an early- and late-day increase in shared motion variability across the measurement stations involved.

Figure 5: The 17 extracted components (y-axis) in the temporal domain. Bright-coloured time windows indicate a high scaling of shared variability across measurement stations. The rows of this matrix served as the input features in the feature selection protocol described hereafter.

3.2 Feature extraction

After some preprocessing, we transformed the ground motion data into 10-second intervals and each interval is assigned a label 0 if there is no earthquake or 1 if there is at least one. To prepare the data for the detection we extracted several statistical features such as the mean, standard deviation, maximum absolute distance, median absolute deviation, skewness, kurtosis and quantiles corresponding to 1%, 10%, 25%, 50%, 75%, 90%, and 99%.

Using these features, we aim to differentiate earthquake waveforms from normal ground activity or noise. Features like the max absolute distance and 99% quantiles can indicate the existence of large amplitudes caused by an earthquake while skewness and kurtosis show deviations from a normal distribution. A normal distribution is expected for noise in seismic data so these can be used to discriminate between noise and signal. A distribution with high skewness (positive or negative) will be shifted towards the left or right tail respectively. A distribution with high kurtosis corresponds to a peaked distribution while a low kurtosis value shows a

Figure 6: The output of a feature selection protocol using classification-based machine-learning. Red dots indicate high values of the corresponding feature while blue dots indicate low values. The x-axis shows the Shapley value of the respective feature (y-axis) on the target variable. Note, there will be one of these for each target variable in this case the target variable will be the occurrence of an earthquake in a time window.

flat one. Additionally, we decided to use only earthquakes of magnitude 2 or higher to avoid a lot of interference with standard data noise.

After this preprocessing we end up with one table where each row corresponds to a 10-second window waveform and the columns contain the statistical features mentioned. The labels for each time window are stored on a separate array to be used in the detection algorithms. With more time to dedicate to this project, a wider list of features could be considered in order to differentiate earthquake signals more effectively from background events.

Figure 7: Left: Spatial patterns of inter-dependencies between measurement stations [From Top-Bottom: Feature 12, 9 and 0]. Right: A geographic mapping of the corresponding spatial networks. The top map illustrates how CLC was a focal recording point. The middle map shows a similar pattern focused around the DTP measurement station. Finally, the bottom map described how both SRT and TOW2 captured shared variability in ground motion signals with several other stations.

Figure 8: Temporal patterns of share seismic activity across measurement stations

4 Seismic detection methods

The rapid detection of earthquakes is an important tool to develop, both for use in alert systems in earthquake-prone areas and as part of wider algorithms. Seismometer data files are increasingly large, with a single day in this project’s dataset having more than 8,640,000 data points for a single station operating at 100 Hz. The vast majority of these data points do not contain any seismic events greater than magnitude 2 (up to 99% in the July 4th dataset) and so triggering methods to locate earthquakes for all of the dataset is not only largely useless but also computationally expensive.

This section of the report, therefore, presents preliminary results on supervised machine learning-based detection algorithms, in order to classify the dataset into sections with and without earthquakes, reducing the amount of data that would need to be analysed by several orders of magnitude.

4.1 Data pre-processing

Before training, a number of preprocessing steps had to be undertaken in order to increase the effectiveness and convergence rate of the machine learning algorithms. Only data from the 4th of July was used due to the size of the full dataset. Data from each station, in only the HHE orientation, were combined into one array. The data was then grouped

into time windows of 10 seconds, corresponding to 1000 data points. Features described earlier were extracted from each of these data windows, and a list of labels was constructed for each time window, using the provided list of seismic events. The output of this was a list of pure seismogram time series for each time window, a list of features for each time window, and a list of the categories for each time window. This was expressed as a series of 0's and 1's, with a 0 indicating not an earthquake and 1 indicating an earthquake. The data was also normalised using sklearn's StandardScaler class, to make convergence quicker.

One major challenge when classifying earthquakes is the unbalanced nature of the dataset. As shown in Figure 9, the number of non-earthquakes far exceeds the number of earthquakes.

Figure 9: Number of non-earthquakes vs Number of earthquakes. Note the heavy skew in the data towards the non-earthquakes.

This presents a key issue when evaluating the model's performance: if the network assigned the 'Not an Earthquake label' to every time window, the unbalanced nature of the dataset means that the accuracy – the ratio of correct predictions to total predictions - of the network would still be very high. A model that detects no earthquakes would not be useful to this problem, yet if one only looks at accuracy, the model would seem to be operating at near-perfect performance.

To have a more comprehensive view of the model, two metrics will be considered in the following sections. One is the Recall – the ratio of True Positives to the sum of True Positives and False Negatives – which can be thought of as the proportion of actual positives that are identified correctly. The other is the confusion matrix (Figure 10) defined below¹:

Confusion Matrix

	Actually Positive (1)	Actually Negative (0)
Predicted Positive (1)	True Positives (TPs)	False Positives (FPs)
Predicted Negative (0)	False Negatives (FNs)	True Negatives (TNs)

Figure 10: Definition of a Confusion Matrix

For this problem, it is preferable for the number of True Positives to be high and the False Negatives to be low. This often comes at the expense of having a higher proportion of False Positives, but in detection problems, having a higher rate of false positives is acceptable so long as it is still much smaller than the rate of True Negatives, as missing earthquakes are seen as a worse result than over-labelling.

To mitigate the effect of data imbalance, the majority class - 'Not an Earthquake' - was undersampled so that the counts of the two classes were the same. This was done using the RandomUnderSampler Class from the Python package imbalance-learn. While this vastly improved model performance in all cases, it does reduce the amount of training data by three orders of magnitude, an issue that will be discussed more in section 5.3.

¹Source: <https://glassboxmedicine.com/2019/02/17/measuring-performance-the-confusion-matrix/>

4.2 Preliminary results

K nearest neighbours (KNN)

The first algorithm that was trialled was the K-Nearest neighbours algorithm. This is a non-parametric supervised method, which has been applied to classification, regression and dimension reduction, and works by making predictions based on the closest training examples in the feature space. The aim of the K-NN algorithm is to find a number (K) of the closest training examples to the input data point, and then use the most common class label among these examples to make a prediction for the input data point. The value of K is a hyperparameter that needs to be chosen based on the specific problem.

The input data points to the method were the seismogram time series in 10-second chunks, and these data points were grouped according to their pre-assigned category and input to the network as a series of 0s and 1s. A different set of input data points model, with the model labelling each time window as an earthquake or not an earthquake, and outputting the corresponding list of 0s and 1s. The optimum value for the hyperparameter K was chosen from the result of a cross-validated grid search varying K from 1 to 40. This was done using the GridSearchCV class from scikit-learn. The best results were obtained using a value of K=17, the results of which are displayed in Tables 1 and Figure 11.

Metric	Score
Accuracy	0.847
Recall	0.667

Table 1: Summary metrics for KNN

These results are promising, as the algorithm is finding the majority of the earthquakes, but the false negative rate indicates the model is miss-labelling 340 seconds of seismic data, information from which could be crucial in the scenario of a major earthquake. The use of raw seismic data is also problematic, as the use of these large datasets makes training and prediction computationally expensive. For this reason, the use of computed features rather than raw data was implemented in the following trials. Seven features were used (Maximum value, Max Absolute

Figure 11: Confusion matrix for KNN predictions.

Difference, 99th percentile, 1st percentile, minimum value, skew, and kurtosis), which reduced the size of the input data by a factor of 142.

Support vector machines (SVMs)

The second algorithm that was trialed was the Support Vector Machine. This machine takes a set of features and a list of corresponding labels as input and then after training, will output prediction for the category for a given input point. SVMs use a kernel function to project the data from a high-dimensional space to an alternate space of n dimensions where the points are linearly separable. The SVM then considers each data point as an n -dimensional vector and constructs $(n-1)$ -dimensional hyperplanes that can separate the data. To find the best classifier out of these hyperplanes, the SVM calculates the distance between each hyperplane and the nearest point from each class, labelled the support vectors. This distance is labelled the margin and the SVM selects the maximum one,

maximising the SVM’s ability to predict the classification of unseen data points. This hyperplane is called the Maximum-Margin Hyperplane, and in general, the larger the Maximum-Margin Hyperplane, the lower the generalisation error of the SVM.

Training data for the SVM consisted of the list of seven features for each time window, as well as the labels for each time window. Two different approaches to using SVMs were tried: one consisting of a single SVM model and the other consisting of a bootstrap aggregation (bagging) of 20 models. These models performed poorly, with the bootstrap aggregation missing fewer events than the single model, albeit at the expense of a higher False Positive rate as shown in Tables 2 & 3 and Figures 12 & 13. One possible reason for this is the noise inherent in seismic data. Pre-filtering the data to remove noise may improve SVM performance, but this is an additional step that could be computationally expensive, and for this reason, SVMs may not be suitable for this problem.

Metric	Score
Accuracy	0.966
Recall	0.211

Table 2: Summary metrics for single SVM results.

Metric	Score
Accuracy	0.670
Recall	0.484

Table 3: Summary metrics for bagged SVM results.

Random forest classifiers

The third and final algorithm that was trialled was the Random Forest (RF) algorithm, an ensemble learning method that constructs a multitude of decision trees at training time and outputs the class, which is the mode of the classes of the individual trees. Each decision tree in the Random Forest is built by recursively splitting the data based on the input features until a stopping criterion is met. The stopping criterion could be a maximum tree depth or a minimum number of samples per leaf. The

Figure 12: Confusion matrix for single SVM predictions.

splits are chosen based on the feature that maximises the Gini index, which measures the impurity of the data at a given node. There are several advantages to an ensemble approach to training, with the most relevant to this dataset being the ability to handle noisy data.

Training data for the RF algorithm was identical to that of the SVMs. Two hyperparameters were considered in this preliminary analysis: the number of estimators (number of trees in the forest) and the minimum samples per node (minimum number of training samples in each tree leaf), which were set to 10000 and 55, respectively. The random forest approach yielded the best results, only missing 17-time windows with earthquakes as shown in Table 4 and Figure 14.

Metric	Score
Accuracy	0.780
Recall	0.809

Table 4: Accuracy and recall results for Random Forest

Figure 13: Confusion matrix for bagged SVM predictions.

While the True Positive rate was the highest for this approach, the rate of false positives was also fairly high. Although it is still much lower than the rate of True Negatives, further work should aim to reduce this rate, possibly by more hyperparameter tuning or using additional features.

4.3 Further work

Based on the preliminary results presented here, the best approach for earthquake detection is the random forest classification, followed by the k-nearest neighbour approach. We tentatively suggest SVMs are unsuitable for this problem due to the noisy nature of seismic data but this requires further analysis to confirm. The time constraints inherent in these events mean that not all potential avenues were explored.

In both recommended approaches, the next logical step would be developing a tool to stitch together adjacent time windows identified as containing an earthquake, to produce the full time series of the event for

Figure 14: Confusion matrix for Random Forest predictions.

the location part of this project, linking the two methods into one workflow. Additionally, adapting this method for use on continuous real-time data would also be advantageous for use in earthquake-prone areas to provide early warning systems. As stated in the data pre-processing section, undersampling the majority class results in a massive reduction in the amount of training data available to the model. This issue was compounded further due to time constraints, as only one day's worth of data was used in the interest of keeping run times low. Further work should therefore include adding all of the 24 days available to the training data to make the model predictions more robust. Tuning more hyperparameters for both approaches may also result in better model performance.

5 Seismic location methods

The ability to locate an earthquake from seismic measurements is a very important tool for understanding volcano dynamics and eruption likelihood, understanding glacial processes and mapping out fault networks to then identify regions likely to suffer damage in the event of a large earthquake. The following details three approaches by the DSG trialled to solve this problem: a traditional machine learning method in the form of random forest regression; and then two deep learning methods, a convolutional neural network (CNN) and a physics-informed neural network (PINN).

5.1 Predicting the location of the Earthquake

Using a random forest regressor, the location (latitude and longitude) of an earthquake was predicted. The model was trained using the maximum amplitude and the time this occurred for a fixed window (10s) across all stations on the 4th of July.

Figure 15: Comparison of the performance of the Random Forest Regressor in predicting the location (latitude versus longitude) of an earthquake. The model performance using the raw values of the training data (left) as compared to using standardised values of the training data (right) is shown.

The model generally performed well in predicting the location of an earthquake (Figure 15). Lower mean squared errors (MSE), mean absolute errors (MAE) and root mean squared errors (RMSE) were associated with the longitudes compared with the latitudes. Standardising the data improved the results mainly for the longitudes, but not significantly in the case of the latitudes. The performance metrics are summarised in Table 5.

Metric	Lat	Lon	Lat (std.)	Lon (std.)
MSE	0.186	0.109	0.223	0.0928
MAE	0.391	0.246	0.427	0.229
RMSE	0.431	0.330	0.472	0.305

Table 5: Comparison of the model performance in predicting the location (latitude and longitude) of an earthquake. The results for the raw data and standardised are also shown.

5.2 CNNs for detection and location

On observing that the dataset could locate earthquake epicentres, we then explored state-of-the-art methods using a supervised deep-learning approach. We found multiple architectures that could be used for simultaneous earthquake detection and location, which utilise differences in waveform among the three components (HHE, HHN, and HHZ) and the time difference of the earthquake’s signal arrival at the different seismometers [6]. This approach worked very naturally with the datasets we were given.

One intriguing methodology applied convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to determine the probabilities of earthquake epicentres within a particular region [7]. In their approach, a clustering algorithm was utilised to create six distinct regions of interest, and the seismograms recorded at each station were processed through a CNN to classify the earthquake’s region of origin. However, this method had some limitations such as its reliance on a fixed number of detectors and locating the event in a broad region detection instead of precise location detection. In this section, we sought to explore this methodology and address its limitations, by extending the scope of this approach by outputting specific longitude and

latitude values and accommodating greater detector flexibility in terms of input size.

Architecture

We based our architecture on the region detector introduced in [7], which we adapted for the regression task of earthquake location instead of classification. In addition to this architecture, we incorporated the location of the detectors into the model before the fully connected layer. We also implemented batch normalisation and dropout techniques to enhance the model's performance and make it more generalisable and avoid overfitting. By doing so, our model can make predictions even if a detector is offline on a particular day.

Loss function

To ensure that both longitude and latitude were minimised in our model, we created a custom loss function. The objective of this function was to minimise the distance between the predicted values while still maintaining variance. For our final model, we implemented the following loss function:

$$L = w1 * \text{MSE}(\text{long}) + w2 * \text{MSE}(\text{lat}) + w3 * (\text{var}(\text{long}) + \text{var}(\text{lat}))$$

where $w1$, $w2$, and $w3$ are weights to be varied, var is the variance, lat is latitude, long is longitude, and MSE is the mean squared error. These weights were varied in the analysis.

Data

We utilised data from the 24-hour period during a significant earthquake on July 4th, 2019 [2]. This data included the seismograms for all stations, the station locations, and the labels were the earthquake locations from the high-resolution earthquake catalogue provided.

Data augmentation

To normalise the location data, both for the earthquake locations and seismometer locations, the longitudes and latitudes were scaled to values between 0 and 1.

To improve earthquake detection accuracy, we filtered the earthquake location data to only include those with a magnitude of one or higher. This is because earthquakes with lower magnitudes are often overshadowed by seismometer noise.

To preprocess the seismic displacement data, we performed batch-wise normalisation and segmented the amplitudes into 10-second time windows centred around the earthquake events identified by the earthquake catalog. During our investigation, we explored the impact of reducing the sampling rate to determine the minimum rate necessary for accurate earthquake location. To achieve this, we performed an additional augmentation on the displacement data by varying the sampling rate from 10 Hz up to the maximum of 100 Hz.

Training

Due to time constraints, the model was only allowed to train for 20 epochs, with the best-performing epoch saved and used for the results.

Approximations for explainability

To help this analysis be approachable for non-geophysics experts, an approximation for the longitude and latitude was used in the analysis to convert the displacements to kilometers:

$$\text{distance (km)} = \text{displacement (latitude)} \times 111.32$$

For the longitude, we assumed a latitude of 36.7783 degrees (the approximate latitude of Sacramento, California) and the average radius of the Earth to be 6,371 km:

$$\text{distance (km)} = \cos(36.7783) \times 2\pi \times 6,371 \text{ km} \times \frac{\text{displacement (longitude)}}{360}$$

Results

Model	Hz	Minimum Magnitude	W1	W2	Lat. Err.	Long. Err.
1	100	1	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.0558
2	50	1	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.0794
3	10	1	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.0559

Table 6: CNN model performance with downsampling

In the first set of experiments in Table 6, we explored the effect of downsampling the frequency. Interestingly, we found that there was not a linear relationship between the model's performance and the downsampling of the frequency. In fact, we observed similar performance between the models with sampling rates of 100Hz and 10Hz and lower performance at 50 Hz. This could be due to the ratio between these models being more comprehensible for the downsampling algorithm, allowing it to retain much more data. It is noteworthy that the model could still accurately locate the earthquake even with much lower sampling rates.

Model	Min Mag	W1	W2	W3	Lat. Err.	Long. Err.
4	100	1.0	1.0	0.1	0.0627	0.0812
5	100	1.0	1.0	0.1	0.0866	0.102

Table 7: Varying Magnitude

We then proceeded to investigate how the model performed when we altered the definition of an earthquake from a minimum magnitude of 1 to 2 as seen in Table 7. It was anticipated that the model would perform better with a higher magnitude, but this was not observed. This lack of improvement may be due to the reduction in available data when only using earthquakes with magnitude 2 or higher, which makes for an unfair comparison.

	Lat. (deg)	Long. (deg)	Lat. (km)	Long. (km)
mean	0.0627	0.0812	6.98	5.46
std	0.0556	0.109	6.19	7.34
min	0.00360	0.0001	0.399	0.0048
25%	0.0266	0.0182	2.96	1.23
50%	0.0433	0.0393	4.82	2.64
75%	0.0770	0.0756	8.57	5.09
max	0.241	0.374	26.8	25.1

Table 8: Model 1 Error by Latitude and Longitude.

Table 8 shows the results of Model 1, the best-performing model. We observed that it achieved a mean latitude error of 7.00 km and a longitude error of 5.46 km after just 20 epochs. The model's performance was impressive, as it managed to get as close as 0.01 km in latitude and 0.40 km in longitude for some event locations. However, there were some data points that significantly deviated from the mean errors. Upon plotting the data in Figure 16, we discovered that these outliers were located very far from the epicentre of the large earthquake that occurred that day. As the model was trained on limited data, it resulted in bias against these far-out earthquakes. Additionally, the plot showed that the data were clustered together, which requires further exploration.

Conclusions

The convolutional neural network showed great potential as a method for earthquake location, achieving a mean latitude error of 0.0627 (7.00 km) and a longitude error of 0.0812 (5.46 km) after only 20 epochs. Moreover, the down-sampling techniques demonstrated stability, showing insignificant performance reduction. However, increasing the minimum magnitude led to instability, which could be due to the reduction in data. To investigate whether the reduction in robustness was due to the decrease in data points, these two outcomes could be combined to incorporate more data while keeping the future model training less computationally expensive. However, the approach showed much promise in these initial findings.

The earthquake location output displayed significant bias, with all data

Figure 16: A plot showing the predicted and actual locations of the earthquake epicenters

points found being clustered in the main earthquake location from July 4th when a large earthquake and aftershocks occurred around the Ridgecrest area. However, incorporating additional data from multiple days could potentially remove these issues since the focus would not be so localised. Another potential solution to improve the variance in the results would be to explore the use of custom losses to heavily penalise the strong localisation of data.

To further improve the earthquake location model, a few data points were observed at the edges of the map which raises questions about whether the model did not detect the earthquake or if it was actually outside the coordinate system. As the next steps, the area used could be expanded and an additional step could be added to explore whether an earthquake was detected or not. This could involve adding a separate results section

for data not found, which could help to better understand the model's limitations and improve its overall performance.

Overall, this method appears to be promising and introduces a novel technique by incorporating seismometer location data to improve the model's localisation. There are several methods that could be employed to expand and further explore this study, which could demonstrate significant potential in locating earthquakes. With additional data and further fine-tuning, this approach could be highly beneficial in accurately locating earthquakes.

5.3 PINN for locating earthquakes

According to ray tracing theory, the governing equation for the travel time Earthquake wave goes through a medium is the Eikonal equation having the form

$$\|\nabla_r T_{s \rightarrow r}\|^2 = \frac{1}{V(\vec{x}_r)^2}$$

where, $\|\cdot\|^2$ is the Euclidean norm, \vec{x}_s the point source location, \vec{x}_r the receiver location, $T_{s \rightarrow r}$ the travel time through medium from source location to receiver location, $V(\vec{x}_r)$ the velocity of the medium at the receiver location, and ∇_r the gradient at receiver location.

Different from the purely data-driven deep learning methods, here we present a Physics-informed Neural Network (PINN) solver to address hypocenter localisation problems. In the frame of PINN, earthquake hypocenter localisation is formulated as an optimisation process by minimising data loss and informed physics loss. Here we design a specific architecture for PINN with two separated neural networks, one deeper neural network for representing the solution of the Eikonal equation, that is travel time $T_{s \rightarrow r}$, one simpler neural network for representing the velocity distribution.

$$\begin{aligned} T_{s \rightarrow r} &= f_{\theta_1}(\vec{x}_s, \vec{x}_r) \\ V(\vec{x}_r) &= g_{\theta_2}(\vec{x}_r) \end{aligned}$$

The structure of PINN is illustrated in Figure 17. The total loss function is

$$\mathcal{L}(\vec{x}_s, t_0, \theta_1, \theta_2) = \frac{1}{N_I} \sum_{\vec{x}_r^* \in I} \left| \|\nabla T_{s \rightarrow r}(\vec{x}_s, \vec{x}_r^*)\|^2 - \frac{1}{V(\vec{x}_r^*)^2} \right|^2 + \frac{1}{N_{obs}} \sum_{\vec{x}_{obs}} |f_{\theta}(\vec{x}_s, \vec{x}_{obs}) - T_{s \rightarrow r}(\vec{x}_{obs})|^2$$

where t_0 is the origin time of the Earthquake.

Figure 17: Structure of PINN for the Earthquake location.

Stochastic learning algorithms and automatic differentiation techniques are used to minimise the loss function. The big challenge for this method is it is time-consuming. Due to the late development of this idea in the challenge, it was not able to produce results or be refined. It does, however, offer an avenue for future work.

6 Conclusions and future work

The challenge involved both the detection and location of earthquakes that have generated detectable waves recorded at nearby seismometers. If successful, this would be useful for studying many natural environments such as volcanoes, glaciers and prospective geothermal sites. The challenge was divided into a location and detection task by the participants.

The detection group trialled several traditional machine learning approaches after feature extraction from 10-second time windows. Of the models trialled, random forests had the best precision and recall. Future avenues for this approach would be testing how well the model generalised to other environments, such as signals from volcanoes and exploring which features are the most important. An approach using just the raw data and the mutual information between the time series recorded at different seismometers at the same time. When mutual information was high, this was taken as a seismic detection. This approach highlighted the temporal pattern of high seismic activity over the course of the day. Future work with this approach would involve exploring the cause of this temporal variation and applying mutual information theory to larger datasets in different environments.

The outstanding performer in the location task was the use of convolutional neural networks to directly predict the longitude and latitude of the earthquake from the ground motion time series and locations of the stations. This approach scored an accuracy on the order of kilometers which is comparable to modern algorithms. Such good accuracy is exciting as there is a lot of room to improve the architecture and expand the application to explore the generalisability of the approach. The generalisability avenue should be explored in more detail with a larger dataset and other architectures trialled.

This hackathon has resulted in several promising avenues from using mutual information theory to detect increases in seismicity to using the raw data to locate earthquakes. These have the potential to provide new approaches to detect and locate earthquakes more accurately and faster than before which has significant implications for eruption monitoring, earthquake response and geothermal activity monitoring.

7 Team members

Naomi Shakespeare-Rees is a first-year PhD student at the University of Leeds and is the facilitator on this project. She contributed to this project by developing the earthquake detection methods, supporting the group to collaborate effectively and ensuring communications within the group and to the DSG Leaders are clear.

David O'Reilly is a PhD student at the University of Leeds. He contributed to work on extracting spatiotemporal patterns of seismicity using network information theory.

Joanne Sheppard is a Research Software Engineer at Durham University. She contributed to the work exploring earthquake detection and location using convolutional neural networks.

Michael Baidu is a PhD graduate from the University of Leeds and a Data Scientist at the Leeds Institute for Data Analytics (LIDA), University of Leeds. He worked on the prediction of earthquake locations using random forests.

Christos Vlahos is a PhD graduate from Durham University. He contributed to this project by performing data preprocessing, feature extraction and helping with the detection algorithm development.

Longwei Chen is a visiting researcher at the University of Leeds. He contributed to this project by presenting a PINN solver for earthquake hypocenter localisation problem.

Jamie Ward is a research fellow at the University of Leeds and is the principal investigator and challenge owner on this project. He contributed to this project by mentoring the participants, providing expert knowledge, and reviewing the report.

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